

Which Prompting Technique is Better? Improving Vibe Coding Code Quality with Efficient Prompt Design for Web Front-End Development

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Abstract - This paper examines the impact of different prompting techniques or strategies on code quality in web front-end development using large language models (LLMs) for vibe coding. While LLMs have shown strong capabilities in generating functional code, the effectiveness of different prompting paradigms remains underexplored in practical development workflows. We address this gap by comparing two widely discussed approaches: zero-shot prompting and prompt chaining. In the zero-shot paradigm, the entire specification, including layout, styling, and logic, is combined into a single comprehensive instruction, requiring the model to synthesize multiple constraints simultaneously. In contrast, prompt chaining divides the specification into sequential sub-tasks, with each intermediate output informing the next, simulating an iterative development process. Our experimental evaluation measures code correctness, maintainability, and adherence to design requirements for both techniques. Results show that prompt chaining consistently improves modularity and reduces error propagation, while zero-shot prompting offers faster generation but at the expense of computer code structural consistency. These findings highlight the trade-offs between efficiency and quality in LLM-assisted front-end development and provide actionable insights for optimizing prompting techniques in real-world coding environments. The codebase created for this research is available at: https://github.com/mhorvat/vibecoding_frontend

Keywords - Large Language Models; Prompt Engineering; Zero-Shot Prompting; Prompt Chaining; Web Front-End Development

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) into the software development lifecycle has started a major paradigm change in the field of software engineering [1]. LLMs are becoming proactive virtual co-developers in application design, code implementation, refactoring, debugging, and testing, and they are no longer strictly limited to autocompletion [2]. The term “vibe coding” refers to an emerging software development paradigm in which developers express implementation intent in natural language and delegate much of the coding to GenAI [3]. Vibe coding become increasingly popular as a result of this

rapid evolution [4]. By lowering the barrier to entry for code developers, this approach enables individuals with little formal programming experience to develop software artifacts [5].

Despite the widespread adoption of LLM-based coding assistants [6], because of the fast pace of development there is currently a significant lack of rigorous, comparative studies analyzing their performance and technical characteristics from a software engineering perspective [7] [8].

Furthermore, in the paradigm of vibe coding, the natural language prompt serves as the primary interface between human intent and machine execution. However, the semantic structure of these prompts, specifically the temporal and logical distribution of instructions, remains a critical variable in determining the quality of the generated software artifacts. Before assessing the comparative capabilities of specific LLMs for vibe coding, it is methodologically imperative to establish an optimal prompting technique or prompting strategy, as it is also called [9] [10].

This study evaluates addresses this gap by evaluating two prompting techniques prevalent in current literature: 1) zero-shot prompting (single-turn) and 2) prompt chaining (multi-turn prompts) for web front-end code development [9] [10]. In this experimental design the **zero-shot prompting** approach consolidates the entire functional specification, including layout, styling, and logic, into a single, long and comprehensive instruction set. It relies on the model's ability to simultaneously synthesize multiple constraints without intermediate feedback. On the other hand, the **prompt chaining** approach decomposes the specification of a web front-end into a logical sequence of discrete sub-tasks (e.g., structural scaffolding, component styling, logic implementation). Each output serves as the input context for the subsequent prompt, simulating an iterative development lifecycle as in a trial-and-error approach in programming.

Research objectives of the presented study are: **Q1:** To compare the effectiveness of zero-shot prompting and prompt chaining paradigms in generating web front-end

code using LLMs; **Q2**: To evaluate code quality using metrics such as correctness, modularity, and adherence to design specifications; **Q3**: To analyze the trade-offs between software code efficiency and structural consistency in both zero-shot and prompting prompt chaining paradigms.

This study represents a follow up on a previously reported experiment of ours [11], in which we empirically examined vibe coding as an emerging software development paradigm in which developers express implementation intent in natural language and delegate much of the coding to generative AI. In this previous study GPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 Pro were compared on three front-end web development tasks of increasing complexity using both zero-shot prompting and evaluated the resulting codebases with a mixed-method framework focused on architecture and feature implementation.

Importantly, we were motivated for this line of research by the results of a survey we previously conducted among computer science students [12], which revealed a strong preference for short prompts in a zero-shot paradigm rather than using prompt chaining with illustrative examples. Students rarely write long instructions and frequently focus only on very short prompts. In order to determine the best practices for LLM-assisted programming methodologies, it was necessary to empirically assess how these prompting tendencies correspond with quality of the generated code.

II. TAXONOMY OF VIBE CODING INTERACTION PARADIGMS: SHOTS AND CHAINS

To rigorously evaluate the efficacy of LLMs in software engineering, it is essential to establish a precise vocabulary for the various modes of human-computer interaction, i.e., “vibing”. In the domain of prompt engineering, two distinct dimensions formally define the nature of the input: a) the

informational context (quantified in “shots”) and b) the interaction structure (quantified in “chains”) [9] [10].

While often used interchangeably in colloquial discourse, these terms represent very different control mechanisms that influence model behavior in fundamentally different ways.

A. The Shot Paradigm: Providing Contextual Examples

The term “**shot**” refers specifically to the inclusion of demonstrative examples within a prompt to guide the model’s execution of a task. It is a measure of the in-context learning provided to the agent before it attempts to generate a solution. The variations are defined as follows:

- **Zero-shot**: In this mode, the user provides explicit instructions and functional requirements but offers no examples of the desired output. The model must rely entirely on its pre-trained knowledge base to infer the correct format and logic. Prompt example: “*Translate this Python function into Rust.*”
- **One-shot**: The user provides the instructions accompanied by exactly one example of a valid input-output pair. This single, so called, shot serves as an anchor, helping the model align its output style or syntax with the user’s expectations. Prompt example: “*Translate this Python function into Rust. Here is an example of how I want the error handling formatted: [Example Code]...*”
- **Multi-shot (or Few-shot)**: The user provides instructions along with multiple examples (typically 2–5). This technique leverages the model’s pattern recognition capabilities, allowing it to infer complex rules or stylistic nuances that may be difficult to articulate in natural language instructions alone.

TABLE I. THE MOST IMPORTANT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN MOST COMMON PROMPTING TECHNIQUES: ZERO-SHOT, ONE-SHOT, MULTI-SHOT, SINGLE-CHAIN AND MULTI-CHAIN, WITH RECOMMENDED PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS IN VIBE CODING.

Term	Category	Definition	Operational Mechanism	Practical Applications
Zero-shot	Shot (Context)	A prompt containing explicit instructions but no examples of the desired output.	The model relies exclusively on its pre-trained internal knowledge to infer the correct logic and format.	Best for general knowledge tasks or when specific styling is not critical (e.g., <i>Write a binary tree in C</i>).
One-shot	Shot (Context)	A prompt containing instructions accompanied by exactly one example of a valid input-output pair.	The single example serves as a style anchor, guiding the model to mimic a specific syntax or tone.	Useful for enforcing a specific structure format (e.g., JSON) or coding style guide without overwhelming the context window.
Multi-shot (Few-shot)	Shot (Context)	A prompt containing instructions and multiple examples (typically 2–5) of desired outputs.	The model utilizes pattern recognition to infer complex rules or nuances that are difficult to describe verbally.	Essential for complex logic tasks where the model must learn a specific pattern of reasoning or data transformation.
Single chain (Single turn)	Chain/Turn (Structure)	A workflow where the entire task specification is submitted in one comprehensive message .	The model must plan, generate, and review the entire artifact in a single pass, maximizing speed but increasing cognitive load.	Efficient for simple scripts or small components ; often leads to errors in complex, multi-file architectures.
Multi-chain (Multi-turn)	Chain/Turn (Structure)	A workflow where the task is decomposed into a sequence of discrete steps (a back-and-forth conversation).	The output of one step becomes the context for the next, allowing for iterative refinement and error correction.	The preferred methodology for Vibe Coding complex applications; ensures structural integrity and enables agentic behavior .

B. The Chain Paradigm: Structuring the Interaction

The term “**chain**” (also referred to as a “**turn**”) delineates the temporal and structural segmentation of the interaction. It refers to the number of discrete exchange (i.e., prompting) cycles between the user and the model required to complete a task.

- **Single-chain:** The user submits the entire request—including all requirements, constraints, and context—in one comprehensive message. The model is expected to generate the final artifact in a single, uninterrupted response. This approach maximizes speed but imposes a high cognitive load on the model’s context window.
- **Multi-chain (or Prompt Chaining):** The user decomposes the task into a sequence of steps, engaging in a back-and-forth conversation. The output of one turn becomes the context for the next. This iterative refinement allows for the validation of intermediate steps (e.g., generating the HTML structure first, then the CSS, then the JavaScript), thereby reducing error propagation and improving architectural coherence.

III. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The objective of the conducted experiment was to empirically compare the performance, generated software components, and interactive behavior of OpenAI’s GPT-4o and Google’s Gemini 2.5 Pro models as would be used by a novice developer for frontend web development tasks. In this approach, we wanted to emulate the approach of an inexperienced developer who had no prior knowledge of more advanced and dedicated vibe coding tools such as Cursor, GitHub Copilot, Lovable or Windsurf. Such developer would spontaneously utilize the most prevalent general foundation models, with OpenAI’s and Google’s being the most commonly employed. Also, the experiment was conducted using both GPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 Pro to ensure cross-model validity.

Furthermore, the experiment was intentionally constrained to foundational web technologies (i.e., HTML, JavaScript, CSS) to isolate the LLMs’ core generative capabilities without the potentially many confusing variables of newer, complex, or less popular frameworks which might have less represented in the LLMs’ training dataset. The chosen computer code stack included:

- HTML: For web document structure.
- CSS with Bootstrap: For frontend styling and responsive layout.
- Plain (“vanilla”) JavaScript: For client-side dynamic logic, deliberately avoiding frameworks like React, Node.js or Vue.js to better assess the models’ basic coding abilities.

In the previously reported study [11], we tasked the models to create three different web frontends: 1) a characteristic web frontends simple paraphrasing and spellchecking tool, 2) moderately complex messenger client, and 3) complex e-commerce web shop. The first two applications required only basic HTML, CSS, and JavaScript without external graphical assets, and we provided the models with a predefined set of images and

icons to be incorporated into the web shop interface. Additionally, a reference picture was provided to the models as a visual template to illustrate the intended appearance of the web shop frontend layout.

In this experiment, we focused only on the “Paraphrasing and spellchecking tool” to isolate the effects of the prompting technique from the model’s inherent coding ability. We employed this task as the prompting technique benchmark for complexity (i.e., as a control) due to its status as the least complex among the three application types examined. By working on the least complex frontend, it was much easier to isolate only the artifacts of the prompting technique concerning code structure and quality. In more complex scenarios, the design choices and programming styles of LLMs might have greater significance.

The sequence of prompts for vibe coding the paraphrasing tool frontend is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The prompt used in the experiment to vibe code the paraphrasing tool web frontend. The prompt consists of five command blocks which were issued simultaneously and sequentially.

The experimental procedure involved two distinct execution scenarios:

1. **Scenario 1 (Zero-Shot):** A single, consolidated prompt (shown in Figure 1) containing five distinct requirement blocks (HTML structure, CSS styling, JavaScript logic, layout constraints, and specific typography) was issued to the models simultaneously.
2. **Scenario 2 (Single-Chain):** The same five requirement blocks were issued sequentially, one after the other. The LLMs were instructed to implement the code iteratively, with each prompt building upon the state of the previous generation.

In Scenario 1, a zero-shot approach without prompt chaining was used to instruct the models through the code development process. In Scenario 2, a single-chain technique utilizing prompt chaining was employed. Specifically, for each application, a predefined set of five sequential prompts defining web features and frontend layout was given to each model. After each prompt, the generated code was analyzed, and corrective follow-up prompts were issued as needed to fix errors or address misinterpretations. This process simulates a realistic, conversational development workflow in the vibe coding paradigm.

All interactions in both scenarios were conducted in English, the *de facto* language for software development and the primary language for LLM training data.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the experiment are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The comparative analysis reveals a significant divergence in computer code quality and architectural integrity between the two prompting techniques.

Figure 2. Comparison of web frontends created by GPT-4o (top) and Gemini 2.5 Pro (bottom) using zero-shot technique.

Figure 3. Comparison of web frontends created by GPT-4o (top) and Gemini 2.5 Pro (bottom) using single-chain technique.

Figures 2 and 3 clearly demonstrate that ChatGPT-4o produced the worst quality in the zero-shot scenario, but significantly improved its quality through the use of prompt chaining technique. The quality of Gemini 2.5 Pro code was also markedly improved through prompt chaining. Overall, prompt chaining resulted in significantly better results and better compliance with instructions for both the ChatGPT and Gemini models. A more detailed examination of the results can be broken down into the analysis of the limitations of zero-shot execution and the effectiveness of prompt chaining.

A. Limitations of Zero-Shot Execution

Under the Zero-Shot condition, both models exhibited signs of contextual saturation. While the generated code was syntactically correct and functionally passable, the user interfaces (UIs) suffered from notable deficiencies:

- **Layout Instability:** Both GPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 Pro struggled to strictly adhere to spatial constraints when presented with simultaneous logic and styling instructions. The resulting layouts were often unbalanced or failed to respect margin and padding specifications.
- **Minimal Viability:** The models defaulted to a literal interpretation, implementing the bare minimum required to satisfy the prompt. The resulting artifacts lacked polish and neglected standard usability heuristics, resembling wireframes rather than production-ready frontends.

B. Efficacy of Prompt Chaining

The Prompt Chaining technique, or strategy, resulted in markedly superior outcomes across both metrics of code quality and user experience (UX).

- **Structural Robustness:** By separating the structure of the web page (HTML) from the styling (CSS), the models produced cleaner and simpler markup. GPT-4o, in particular, demonstrated improved adherence to the Bootstrap grid system when the layout instruction was isolated in its own turn.
- **Emergent Proactivity (The Agentic Shift):** A critical finding was observed in the behavior of Gemini 2.5 Pro. Under the prompt chaining condition, the model transitioned from a passive tool to a proactive agent. It autonomously introduced unrequested but high-value features, such as input field labels (“Original Text” vs. “Paraphrased Text”) and a “Copy to Clipboard” button. This behavior suggests that reducing the immediate cognitive load allows the model to allocate “inference budget” toward anticipating user needs rather than merely satisfying constraints.

V. DISCUSSION

The disparity observed in the conducted experiment supports the hypothesis of cognitive load theory applied to LLMs [13] [14]. This hypothesis postulates that when an instruction set exceeds a certain density of different and heterogeneous constraints (e.g., mixing logic, appearance, UX, and structure), the model's attention mechanism dilutes, leading to hallucination or oversimplification.

In the context of frontend development, prompt chaining functioned as a form of Chain-of-Thought prompting applied to software engineering with web technologies [15] [16] [17]. It forced the model to solve the dependency graph of software development linearly, establishing the DOM structure of the HTML document before manipulating it, and defining styles before applying them. This aligned the generation process with the logical causality of web rendering.

Based on these findings, we unambiguously conclude that Prompt Chaining is the superior methodology for web frontend vibe coding, although it is more difficult to master especially for novice developers. Prompt Chaining is particularly better choice for tasks requiring high-fidelity UI generation. The Zero-Shot approach, while faster, incurs a technical debt in the form of lower code maintainability and poor UX.

The study had limitations that define its scope and point to the next research steps. The experiment isolated prompting effects using a single application type (a paraphrasing/spellchecking tool) and a constrained technology stack; broader generalization requires replication across more complex multi-page UIs, component-based frameworks, and tasks with non-trivial state management. Additionally, outcomes are sensitive to model versioning, sampling stochasticity, and prompt wording; future work should introduce repeated trials, controlled decoding parameters, and automated evaluation pipelines that combine static analysis with behavioral UI tests. A particularly valuable extension of the presented research would be to quantify the total cost of ownership of each workflow, time-to-first-output versus time-to-stable-maintainable-code, because this is the metric that ultimately matters in production environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper sought to answer a practical question that is currently unspecified in the "vibe coding" discourse: when front-end code is generated using LLMs, does the structure of prompting matter enough to justify additional interaction overhead? The empirical outcome is consistent across both evaluated foundation models (GPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 Pro) and within a controlled web front-end task (HTML/CSS/Bootstrap, vanilla JavaScript): prompt chaining (multi-turn requirement decomposition) produces higher-quality codebases than zero-shot prompting (single consolidated specification). The benefit is more than just aesthetic; it manifests in architectural consistency, reduced error propagation, and better adherence to layout and UI constraints, all of which directly correlate to maintainability and downstream modification cost.

Referring to the research objectives, the findings provide clear evidence for **Q1**: prompt chaining is the more effective interaction paradigm for creating a complete front-end artifact under heterogeneous constraints (structure, style, behavior, and typography). For **Q2**, when measured by correctness, modularity, and adherence to design requirements, the chained workflow consistently produces cleaner separation of concerns (HTML structure before CSS styling, followed by JavaScript logic), fewer layout regressions, and less "minimal viability" behavior

that resembles a wireframe rather than a usable interface. For **Q3**, the trade-off is clear: zero-shot prompting prioritizes speed of first output, but the time saved upfront is frequently reintroduced later as technical debt—in the form of inconsistent structure, brittle UI, and corrective work required to regain control of the codebase.

In summary, what can be generally stated regarding vibe coding in both academic settings and the IT sector, and under what circumstances should vibe coding be recommended? Within the academic context, vibe coding shows the potential to transform the educational process [18]. The inclusion of this approach into university-level programming education presents an opportunity to boost engagement, expedite learning, and improve overall teaching quality [11], particularly when utilized within various digital game-based learning frameworks that are designed to simplify and expedite formal student assessment [19]. However, the increasing ease of automatic code generation also introduces new pedagogical challenges, particularly in academic integrity, plagiarism detection, and assessment design [20] [21]. GenAI tools can help students with coding assignments by suggesting, hinting, and generating code snippets, encouraging better coding practices. However, using GenAI in programming education can lead to students becoming too dependent on AI-generated code and failing to understand fundamental concepts, which may negatively impact the long-term sustainability of computer engineering in higher education [22].

Developing robust solutions for detecting vibe-coded laboratory assignments, seminar papers, and student projects is an urgent issue that the academic community must address [23]. From an application design standpoint, vibe coding encourages the creation of responsive, mobile-friendly, and platform-consistent interfaces, allowing students and professionals to create modern frontends with minimum technical overhead [24].

It has recently been shown that the emergence of AI coding tools plays a role in tendency of students to approach programming assignments superficially and focus on fulfilling given requirements rather than focusing on deeper considerations of code quality [25]. Therefore, in the future, it will be necessary to develop clear guidelines, standards, and pedagogical frameworks for the responsible use of vibe coding in education and the workplace. Educational institutions such as schools and universities should consider introducing hybrid teaching models in which vibe coding is used as a complementary tool and not as a substitute for traditional programming instruction. Such hybrid models would preserve the cultivation of fundamental algorithmic thinking while capitalizing on the productivity gains offered by GenAI. In addition, new assessment methods should be developed, potentially combining behavioral analysis, interactive code reviews, live or oral exams, and traceable revision histories to accurately assess student learning outcomes in environments where AI support is ubiquitous.

Vibe coding provides professional developers with opportunities for rapid creation of ideas, cross-domain prototyping, and immediate translation of human intent into code. However, it necessitates stringent quality controls to

guarantee maintainability, reproducibility, and security. With an increasing number of LLMs in development, automated tools for verification, refactoring, and standardization of AI outcomes are emerging as critical elements within the software engineering community.

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